

**Theoretical Development of a Sublingual Oral Formulation of Tissue Plasminogen
Activator for Emergency Thrombolytic Therapy**

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Abstract

A tissue plasminogen activator (tPA) is a protein that catalyzes the breakdown of fibrin clots by converting plasminogen to plasmin, which degrades the clot. This is important in thrombolytic therapy because tPA can catalyze a clot within minutes of entering the bloodstream. However, there are limitations; the only viable way for patients suffering from a myocardial infarction or ischemic cerebrovascular accident to get tPA is for intravenous administration in a hospital setting. The primary purpose of developing a sublingual oral formulation of tPA for emergency thrombolytic therapy is to give people who have a severe myocardial infarction or ischemic cerebrovascular accident a chance of enabling pre-hospital intervention for these types of acute cardiovascular and cerebrovascular events. This theoretical formulation was conceptualized by using the following elements: tPA as the protein to catalyze the clot, a nanocarrier delivery system to deliver tPA to the clots and minimize the risk of hemorrhage, stabilizers to preserve protein structure, pH buffers, permeation enhancers to cross the mucosal membrane, and protective coatings to help tPA from degradation in the oral cavity. It is hypothesized that effective clot dissolution sublingually is comparable to intravenous delivery. This has the potential to revolutionize emergency medicine as we know it, as it provides patients with access to life-saving medication in the event of a myocardial infarction or ischemic cerebrovascular accident. Further investigation is needed to evaluate the pharmacokinetics, pharmacodynamics, and feasibility of this drug and formulation potential in a laboratory setting to determine whether it can be formulated.

Keywords: tissue plasminogen activator, sublingual, formulation, emergency thrombolytic therapy

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Introduction

According to the World Health Organization, “Cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) are the leading cause of death globally” (2021). These are preventable deaths; however, there is no real known at-home emergency device for this type of situation. Aspirin is a standard treatment, but it only stops more clots from forming; it does not catalyze the already existing clots. A tissue plasminogen activator (tPA) is a protein that catalyzes the conversion of plasminogen into plasmin. Once converted to plasmin, the plasmin breaks down the fibrin matrix, which holds the clot in place. This entire process, from entering the bloodstream to recanalization, began at a “median of 17 minutes and was completed at 35 minutes” (Alexandrov et al., 2001). Currently, the only means of tPA being administered is through an intravenous injection in a hospital setting. This presents a significant limitation, as it delays patients who need access to the protein at a critical time. Due to this, these patients who often have time-sensitive cardiovascular or cerebrovascular events may not get life-saving treatment in time. If these issues can be treated more time-sensitively, the mortality risk for these cases could decrease, and the recovery rate could increase. This paper will explore the feasibility of formulating tPA into a sublingual form for emergency thrombolytic therapy for the general population. Therefore, this could jumpstart the catalysis process before emergency services arrive, improving patient outcomes. The purpose of this research is to evaluate the formulation approach for sublingual tPA, which has the potential to revolutionize emergency thrombolytic therapy.

Literature Review

Cardiovascular Disease and Ischemic Cerebrovascular Accidents: An Overview

As stated previously, cardiovascular disease is the leading cause of death in the world. It should also be mentioned that cerebrovascular accidents are the “fifth leading cause of death in the United States and a leading cause of serious long-term disability” (UTMB Health, n.d.). Out of those, approximately “87 percent of all strokes are ischemic strokes” (UTMB Health, n.d.). Due to this, thrombolytic therapy plays a critical role in cardiovascular and cerebrovascular events as it catalyzes the clot, causing recanalization.

The Roles and Mechanisms of tPA

tPA begins its process after being injected into the bloodstream. Once inside the circulatory system, tPA circulates throughout the body until stimulated by a “colocalization” of tPA and plasminogen on fibrin, which acts as a template to promote plasmin generation” (Longstaff et al., 2011). After this, the clot is broken down, which is accomplished by cleaving “the zymogen plasminogen at its Arg561-Val562 peptide bond to form plasmin, a serine protease” (Jilani & Siddiqui, 2023). These are important mechanisms as they result in the immediate catalysis of clots, which directly promote recanalization, saving tissue from further damage. As mentioned earlier, the median time for recanalization is 17-35 minutes, which is another critical factor, as this fast response time stops any further tissue death than what would occur without the role of tPA.

Current Limitations to tPA Administration

According to Genentech USA, Inc., “Activase [a tPA drug] is for intravenous administration only” (2024). This poses a substantial problem as intravenous injection mostly occurs in a hospital setting, denying patients access to the protein until they get to the hospital. After that, it still takes time to get everything set up for the intravenous injection to occur; all of this combined means critical time is wasted, and more tissue death will occur.

Aspirin is a common emergency drug in the case of a myocardial infarction or an ischemic cerebrovascular accident. Aspirin only prevents the development of more clots; it does not catalyze the pre-existing clots. This is caused by “its ability to irreversibly block COX-1. This inhibits production of thromboxane A₂ and thus increases platelet inhibition” (Kurth et al., 2003).

Immediate Thrombolytic Therapeutic Treatment Outcome Implications

If thrombolytic treatment is delayed in a myocardial infarction, every 30 minutes, “there was an increase in risk for death of 7.5% and for ejection fraction <30% of 8.7%” (Williams, 2004). In ischemic intracranial accidents, every 30 minutes, “a favorable mRS shift [a scale used to measure the degree of disability from a cerebrovascular accident] was less likely to occur (OR, 0.93; 95% CI, 0.90 to 0.95)” (Bae et al., 2021). As shown, these delays can significantly worsen patient prognosis if kept untreated; patient mortality is possible.

Alternative Methods of tPA Administration

Research on alternative delivery routes for tPA has been limited to intranasal and oral delivery, with no studies on sublingual or buccal delivery. In the studies where oral and nasal delivery were considered, they were considered challenging. Intranasal delivery is challenging due to “anatomic, physiological and histological characteristics of the nasal cavity, but also due to the underlying mechanisms of drug absorption and delivery through nasal epithelium” (Fortuna, Schindowski, & Sonvico, 2022). Oral delivery has remained a challenge because of “the harsh gastrointestinal tract (GIT) microenvironment and several physiological barriers, including gastrointestinal anatomy factors, biochemistry factors, and physiology factors” (Lou et al., 2023). However, it is agreed that intranasal administration has the highest bioavailability compared to sublingual or oral administration. In a study with the drug Dapoxetine, a drug with poor bioavailability, it was shown that compared to oral

administration, sublingual and intranasal administration had a bioavailability of “124.58% and 611.15%, respectively” (Fouad et al., 2016). However, another study showed that tPA does not work well under intranasal administration because a “Plasminogen zymography showed that acute intranasal delivery of 1.4 or 5.6 mg/kg tat-NBD peptides failed to suppress the HI-induced tPA and uPA activity at 4 h recovery” (Yang et al., 2013). This suggests that intranasal delivery may not be able to inhibit tPA delivery in some contexts. As shown, oral and intranasal delivery will not be able to deliver tPA successfully. Sublingual administration is the only option remaining, and it has not been studied. It is hypothesized that sublingual administration could be better than oral or intranasal administration of tPA. There are rich blood vessels underneath the tongue, supported by the lingual artery, which allows tPA direct access to the circulatory system, instead of going through the digestive and respiratory systems. Hence, allowing faster absorption of the protein and faster clot dissolution. However, it is also hypothesized that sublingual delivery has its pitfalls, as tPA is a large protein, having “an estimated molecular weight of 66.68 kDa” (Long et al., 2015). Meanwhile, the sublingual mucosa “allows for the permeation of molecules as big as 70 kDa” (Fantini et al., 2022). It should also be noted that this comes under heavy scrutiny of permeation enhancers, which should help tPA cross the membrane, but on its own, it would not. Another thing to consider is that tPA is hydrophilic, which is exhibited by producing “purified soluble recombinant protein” (Long et al., 2015). This problem is because “hydrophilic macromolecules with a molecular weight above 500–1000 Da have poor membrane permeability” (Kim, Cheon, & Lee, 2021). The final challenge is the enzymatic barriers in the oral cavity, because of the “harsh conditions of the gastrointestinal (GI) tract, characterized by acidic pH, enzymatic degradation, and limited permeability across the intestinal epithelium” (Chavda & Balar, 2025). The situation is exacerbated because tPA is the most active when the pH ranges from “7.6–8.2, the activity was lower and showed great

variability” (Hamon et al., 1990). At the same time, the pH of saliva ranges from “6.2 to 7.6” (Frothingham, 2018). This means that tPA will not be active in the oral cavity most of the time and has to face the enzymes that could lead to the degradation of tPA. Overall, the most efficient way to administer tPA is sublingually. While there are challenges associated with administering tPA sublingually, numerous benefits can be realized if those challenges are overcome.

Significance of Developing a Sublingual tPA Formulation

It is hypothesized that if a sublingual tPA formulation were to be developed, the impact on the general population would be enormous. It would be the first emergency thrombolytic agent in the general market, causing a decrease in the mortality rate and a decrease in medical burdens. Studies support a decreased mortality rate, as supported by David O. Williams’s study from 2004 and Hee-Joon Bae et al. ’s study from 2021. It is also proven that medical burdens are decreased, as highlighted in Hany Aref et. al’s study: “The results of this study indicate that the treatment of AIS with alteplase during the 4.5-h period after stroke symptoms onset results in substantial cost savings over a 5-year time horizon” (2023). This suggests that if a sublingual tPA formulation were introduced to the general market, the mortality rate and medical burdens would decrease.

State of Current Research

Currently, there are no comprehensive studies on sublingual tPA formulations. This represents a critical gap in research, as this branch of administration has never been hypothesized. This paper is the first research paper to investigate sublingual tPA. This type of formulation should be evaluated to assess its feasibility and the safety of such a formulation. If this formulation were to prove to be feasible and safe, it could be made accessible to the public and cause mortality and healthcare costs to potentially decrease. Overall, if more research and studies are conducted to assess the feasibility and safety of an emergency

sublingual tPA drug, it could transform the medical field and improve patient outcomes.

Methodology

Research Design

The type of research being conducted is purely theoretical; this will focus on the feasibility of formulating sublingual tPA. It also assesses the potential safety concerns and the challenges that sublingual tPA could pose if developed under current pharmaceutical standards in 2025.

Objective of Methodology

The objective of this methodology is to assess whether sublingual tPA could be a viable emergency treatment option, particularly in patients with a higher risk of a myocardial infarction or ischemic cerebrovascular accident. This will evaluate existing literature on tPA pharmacodynamics and pharmacokinetics, analyze sublingual administration, and assess potential challenges in formulation and safety concerns, under current pharmaceutical standards.

Evaluation Criteria for Feasibility

Feasibility is evaluated using the following criteria: molecular weight of tPA, the stability of tPA in the sublingual mucosal membrane, the bioavailability of tPA after crossing the sublingual mucosal membrane, how pH levels are maintained in sublingual tPA, and the risk of hemorrhage in tPA. As previously established, the molecular weight of tPA is 66.68 kDa. The feasibility of the study is determined by examining whether the sublingual mucosal membrane can absorb a protein of 66.68 kDa via permeation enhancers or other methods. Next, it has already been identified that tPA is not stable in the sublingual mucosal membrane; feasibility would depend on whether tPA can become stable in the sublingual mucosal membrane. Also, since it has been previously discussed that tPA is a large molecule, feasibility would be determined if tPA can reach a sustainable bioavailability via crossing the

sublingual mucosal membrane. It was also mentioned that tPA remains the most active at a pH level ranging from 7.6-8.2; feasibility would be evaluated on how this pH would be maintained, once entering the oral cavity, and in packaging. Finally, tPA has a considerable risk of hemorrhage; it has been proven that “Thrombolysis increases the risk of HT [hemorrhagic transformation] by >4-fold” (Lu et al., 2023). Feasibility would have to be assessed if the hemorrhagic risk can be decreased to a level low enough that it is not a common occurrence. If these criteria are met, sublingual tPA should be deemed feasible and formulated.

In-Depth Hypothesis on the Formulation of Sublingual tPA

This medication would be formulated into a tablet form that would dissolve easily, which would help tPA be transported across the sublingual mucosal membrane as efficiently as possible. As previously mentioned, the size of tPA is 66.68 kDa, to overcome this, there are advanced ways to aid tPA in crossing the sublingual mucosal membrane would be to use polyethylene glycol coating, as they can “form a hydrated shell that enhances drug solubility and limits renal filtration, cellular uptake, proteolytic degradation, and immunogenicity” (Greineder et al., 2013). Another coating that could be used is chitosan polysulfate-coated liposomes, because “The coating of liposomes with chitosan or its derivatives improved liposome stability, provided sustained drug release and increased drug penetration across mucus layers” (Sebaaly et al., 2021). Next, additives would be used to increase absorption into the sublingual mucosal membrane, one of these being surfactant binders, most likely a “Pluronic® p123/Syloid® mixture) to enhance tablet disintegration and dissolution. Microencapsulated polysorbate 80 (Sepitrap™ 80) were included in the composition of BESTs [Bilayer Enhanced Sublingual Tablets] to enhance the drug transport through the sublingual mucosa” (El-Setouhy et al., 2015). Chemical permeation enhancers (CPEs) are another functional additive because “mainly due to the establishment of ionic interactions

with the charged groups of the mucosal membrane, thus increasing the diffusion process” (Di Prima et al., 2021). To maintain pH balance, a buffering agent like sodium bicarbonate would work well because “sodium bicarbonate has a good buffer capacity, and the pH of 1 % aqueous solution is approximately 8.31, the other, sodium chloride has no effect on the pH of cooked myofibrillar protein solute. Thus, the pH significantly increased” (Kang et al., 2023). This would help keep the pH of tPA at a stable state during packaging and inside the oral cavity. To minimize the risk of hemorrhage, targeted drug delivery to the site via nanocarriers would be the most viable option, as it “reduces side effects, increases drug stability and prolongs the half-life” (Shen et al., 2021). This would be accomplished “through liposomal membrane destabilization involving membrane fusion upon incubation with activated platelets” (Huang et al., 2019). A targeted nanocarrier delivery system would help guide tPA to the clot, while at the same time lessening the chance of tPA causing hemorrhage. If these methods are implemented, then tPA can cross the sublingual mucosal membrane and catalyze the clot, causing recanalization and reducing the risk of hemorrhage in the patient.

Other Protein Drugs Delivered Sublingually

There are no FDA-approved sublingual protein drugs, but there have been trials with other proteins to be delivered sublingually. One of these proteins is Bovine Serum Albumin (BSA), which has a “molecular weight of 66 kDa” (Balkani et al., 2016). As shown, BSA has a molecular weight similar to that of tPA. Trials with BSA being administered sublingually have shown that “In addition to peptide drugs, the novel peptides were shown to enable sublingual absorption of larger proteins with molecular weights from 22 to 150 kDa in mice, including...bovine serum albumin (BSA)” (Wu et al., 2024). Overall, while there may not currently be any FDA-approved sublingual protein drugs, the studies in which sublingual protein drugs were used are promising.

Research Limitations

The research being conducted is purely theoretical and limited by the lack of experimental data on tPA's absorption through the sublingual mucosal membrane, its stability, and delivery methods.

Expected Outcomes***Hypothesis***

Sublingual administration of tPA is a practical and feasible method of thrombolytic therapy, as long as issues such as stability, permeability, molecular weight, bioavailability, hemorrhagic risk, and stable pH levels are successfully addressed.

Predicted Outcomes if Successfully Formulated

tPA should be able to cross the sublingual mucosa effectively with the help of chitosan polysulfate-coated liposomes, polyethylene glycol coating, other surfactant binders, and CPEs. tPA should also be able to maintain stability with buffering agents such as sodium bicarbonate, which will help tPA maintain a relative pH ranging from 7.6-8.2 so that it remains in its most active state during packaging, inside the oral cavity, and absorbed through the sublingual mucosa, which will help the clot be catalyzed faster. Another factor considered is that sufficient bioavailability will be produced to catalyze the clot as tPA on its own, without any polyethylene glycol coating, chitosan polysulfate-coated liposomes, surfactant binders, and CPEs, has "Zero oral bioavailability" (Yartsev, 2021). It is hypothesized that if these enhancers are added, there may be a chance at achieving 5-10% bioavailability. The time of clot lysis completion for tPA, which has a 100% bioavailability, had a "mean time...[of] 55 and 48 minutes respectively" (Pannell, Li, & Gurewich, 2015). If optimistic, and clot lysis is complete at 48 minutes, if only 10% of the drug is available, it would take roughly 480 minutes for clot lysis to complete. This is not feasible, which means the dose

must be raised tenfold to twentyfold to match the dose of intravenous administration. This does raise the risk of hemorrhage, but it is hypothesized that the trade-off is worth the risk, especially with nanocarrier delivery, because “Approximately 1 in 6 patients has a better and 1 in 35 has a worse outcome as a result of therapy” (Saver et al., 2009). Nanocarrier delivery could put it back at that same 1 in 35 risk; this risk could be lowered with adjunctive therapies such as PEGylation and liposomal delivery. As previously mentioned, nanocarriers would lower the risk of hemorrhage and lower systemic exposure, giving the patient a greater chance of recovery. Finally, if all of these methods prove to work correctly and with each other, sublingual tPA could be a viable emergency thrombolytic therapy.

Hypothesis Justification

Sublingual administration is a viable option for a protein with a molecular weight of 66.68 kDa because polysulfate-coated liposomes, chitosan polysulfate-coated liposomes, surfactant binders, and CPEs will help tPA be able to cross the sublingual mucosal membrane, as supported by Doaa Ahmed El-Setouhy et al.’s study from 2015, Carine Sebaaly et al.’s study from 2021, Colin F. Greineder et al.’s study from 2013, and Giulia Di Prima et al.’s study from 2021. Protein stability is maintained with sodium bicarbonate as it has a good buffer capacity, and would maintain the pH, as supported by Zhuang-Li Kang et al.’s study from 2023. While bioavailability is maintained effectively by increasing the dosage, it delivers the effect like intravenous administration. While increasing the dosage may increase hemorrhagic risk, this is ultimately prevented by using nanocarriers for targeted delivery, significantly decreasing the risk of hemorrhage as shown by Ying Huang et al.’s 2019 study. These strategies will undoubtedly result in a viable sublingual tPA emergency thrombolytic, as long as they are proven viable.

Long-Term Implications

If this method is proven to be successful, it will enable faster treatment for myocardial infarctions and ischemic cerebrovascular accidents. Additionally, intravenous administration decreases, which is essential because it “reduces patient dependency on hospital facilities and reduces drug delivery-related healthcare costs and resource use. It is also less time-consuming and minimizes the discomfort associated with intravenous infusion” (Jonaitis et al., 2021). It would improve patient outcomes, as shown by David O. Williams’ study from 2004 and Hee-Joon Bae et al.’s study from 2021. Moreover, it will result in lower hospital costs, as supported by Hany Aref et al.’s study from 2023. Overall, if sublingual tPA proves to be a viable treatment option for emergency thrombolytic therapy. In that case, treatment will be more rapid, less dependent on intravenous administration, patient outcomes will improve, and hospital costs will be lowered.

Discussion

Summary

This paper evaluated the feasibility of formulating sublingual tPA for emergency thrombolytic therapy. The results concluded that sublingual tPA could be formulated if it could bypass the following barriers: degradation in the oral cavity due to enzymatic activity, pH balance, reducing the risk of hemorrhage, producing a sustainable bioavailability, and molecular weight. These issues could be bypassed by using sodium bicarbonate as a pH stabilizer, using nanocarriers for targeted delivery by reducing hemorrhage risk, using permeation enhancers that prevent tPA from enzymatic degradation and help tPA cross the sublingual mucosa, even with its molecular weight, and increasing the dosage, therefore increasing bioavailability. Overall, sublingual tPA could be formulated and be effective if these properties are successfully integrated into tPA.

Interpretation and Implications of Findings

These results imply that tPA could have the potential to be administered sublingually, giving an alternative method of administration and a broader impact on patient outcomes and hospital finances. However, there are major challenges that must be overcome if it can be proven viable. tPA needs to range with a pH from 7.6-8.2 to be its most stable and most active, while at the same time, a buffer like sodium bicarbonate would prevent expiration during packaging and degradation in the oral cavity, this would be a key mechanism to get tPA into the bloodstream, beginning clot lysis and recanalization while also staying stable enough to be administered at any time. Another issue is enzymatic degradation in the oral cavity and the risk of hemorrhage. Nanocarriers would encapsulate tPA from these issues, and bring it to the clot via targeted delivery, reducing the risk of hemorrhage, and keeping tPA as a stable protein so it can perform effectively. tPA is also a huge protein with a size of 66.68 kDa, and cannot permeate the sublingual mucosa on its own, to counter this permeation enhancers such as polyethylene glycol coating, chitosan polysulfate-coated liposomes, Pluronic® p123/Syloid® mixture, microencapsulated polysorbate 80, and CPEs, these could help tPA permeate the sublingual mucosa and enter the bloodstream and begin the process of clot lysis as emergency personnel arrive. Finally, while bioavailability is hypothesized to be very low, ranging from 5-10%, the dosage could be raised ten to twentyfold to achieve the same effect, while increasing the risk of hemorrhage and potentially detrimental side effects, nanocarriers may be able to lower this risk, while at the same time the patient gets the same dose, giving patients critical time before permanent injury or fatality happen. These findings indicate that this could cause the beginning of emergency thrombolytic therapy outside of hospitals, but formulation of the proposed drug, in vitro and in vivo testing, and human trials would have to be conducted to verify this claim.

Comparison with Existing Literature

Studies such as Jiamin Wu et al.'s study from 2024 have shown that proteins with a large molecular weight delivered sublingually, such as BSA, have shown promise for this method of administration. These findings also align with the work of Doaa Ahmed El-Setouhy et al.'s study from 2015, Carine Sebaaly et al.'s study from 2021, Colin F. Greineder et al.'s study from 2013, and Giulia Di Prima et al.'s study from 2021, which described enhancers and the methods of permeation of the sublingual mucosa while avoiding enzymatic degradation. While studies such as Minghua Shen et al.'s from 2021 have shown that nanocarriers risk of reducing side effects from drugs. Other studies, such as Zhuang-Li Kang et al.'s study from 2023, support sodium bicarbonate as a useful pH buffer. Conversely, Alex Yartsev's study from 2021 points out the low oral bioavailability of tPA, with no existing literature to counter this argument. Together, these studies are promising in existing literature, but there are challenges in current literature, such as poor oral bioavailability, which have not been explored deeply enough.

Limitations

Currently, this research is limited by its theoretical framework and the absence of data and experimental validation. There are still multiple variables left to be determined by this paper, and in vitro and in vivo testing and experimental data are critical to determine these variables. Furthermore, these tests and data must be explored to determine if sublingual tPA can be formulated.

Future Directions

Future research should focus on formulating sublingual tPA using covalent conjugation with enzyme inhibitors, polyethylene glycol conjugation, sodium bicarbonate-buffered lyophilized wafers, chitosan polysulfate-coated liposomes, covalent conjugation to cell-penetrating peptides, Pluronic® P123/Syloid® combinations,

ligand-targeted Nanocarriers, stimuli-responsive nanoparticles, microencapsulation with permeation enhancers, cyclodextrin complexes, mucoadhesive nanogels, fast-dissolving sublingual films, and 3D-printed sublingual platforms. After that, research should be focused on in vitro with permeability assays, enzyme activity assays, stability studies, release profiles, cytotoxicity, and biocompatibility, and in vivo testing in rabbits, rodents, dogs, and pigs. The data from these experiments would be assessed from these tests. If testing is proven to be successful, the next step should be human trials by reviewing the data from these trials and assessing the pharmacodynamics and pharmacokinetics of sublingual tPA in humans.

Conclusion

This paper explored the feasibility of sublingual tPA being used as an emergency thrombolytic agent, as long as issues such as molecular weight, pH, hemorrhagic risk, bioavailability, permeability, and stability were fixed and able to be utilized to make tPA a helpful emergency thrombolytic medication. Evidence suggests that enhancers such as polyethylene glycol coating, chitosan polysulfate-coated liposomes, Pluronic® p123/Syloid® mixture, microencapsulated polysorbate 80, and CPEs could help tPA cross the sublingual mucosal membrane, even if it has a molecular weight of 66.68 kDa. Nanocarriers may also reduce the risk of hemorrhage via targeted delivery by only releasing and activating tPA in the presence of fibrin. pH stabilizers like sodium bicarbonate could keep the pH of tPA at 7.6-8.2, keeping it at its most active state. Although the hypothesized bioavailability is 5-10%, the dosage would have to be scaled ten to twentyfold to achieve the same effect, increasing the risk of hemorrhage. However, it is also hypothesized that this risk can be lowered via nanocarrier-targeted delivery. If this approach is proven viable, reliance on intravenous administration would decrease, and hospital priorities could be shifted elsewhere. At the same time, hospital costs would also be lowered, allowing the hospital to buy different resources. This could also buy critical time for patients who need emergency thrombolytic

treatment immediately. However, there are still several challenges before clinical application can be considered. One of these challenges is the difficulty in achieving a high enough bioavailability because “the oral absorption of macromolecules is possible, the bioavailability remains generally low and variable” (Moroz, Matoori, & Leroux, 2016). As mentioned previously, there may also be risks of hemorrhage with dose escalation, but this can be overcome with nanocarriers and their role in targeted delivery. This must be confirmed with multiple in vivo and in vitro testing and human trials. Future studies should focus on and evaluate the pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics of sublingual tPA, clinical outcomes, and cost compared to intravenous administration, combined with different combinations, such as PEGylation, and assess whether the drug would be safe enough to be produced for the general population.

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Competing Interests

The author has no relevant financial or non-financial interests to disclose.

Author Contributions

The author solely conceived, researched, and wrote the manuscript.

Data Availability

No datasets were generated or analyzed during the current study.

References

- Alexandrov, A. V., Burgin, W. S., El-Mitwalli, A., & Grotta, J. C. (2001, June 19). *Speed of Intracranial Clot Lysis With Intravenous Tissue Plasminogen Activator Therapy : Sonographic Classification and Short-Term Improvement*. AHA Journals. Retrieved June 2, 2025, from <https://www.ahajournals.org/doi/10.1161/01.CIR.103.24.2897>
- Aref, H., Nahas, N. E., Elsisy, G. H., Shokri, H., & Roushdy, T. (2023, November 7). *The budget impact of alteplase in the treatment of acute ischemic stroke in Egypt*. Frontiers. Retrieved June 4, 2025, from <https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/neurology/articles/10.3389/fneur.2023.1220615/full>
- Balkani, S., Shamekhi, S., Raoufinia, R., Parvan, R., & Abdolalizadeh, J. (2016, December 22). *Purification and Characterization of Bovine Serum Albumin Using Chromatographic Method*. PubMed. Retrieved June 5, 2025, from <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/28101473/>
- Chavda, V. P., & Balar, P. C. (2025, January 30). *Oral delivery of protein and peptide therapeutics*. PubMed. Retrieved June 4, 2025, from <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/40122651/>
- Di Prima, G., Angellotti, G., Scarpaci, A. G., Murgia, D., D'agostino, F., Campisi, G., & Caro, V. D. (2021, August 31). *Improvement of Resveratrol Permeation through Sublingual Mucosa: Chemical Permeation Enhancers versus Spray Drying Technique to Obtain Fast-Disintegrating Sublingual Mini-Tablets*. PubMed Central. Retrieved June 5, 2025, from <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC8470294/>

- El-Setouhy, D. A., Basalious, E. B., & Abdelmalak, N. S. (2015, June 15). *Bioenhanced sublingual tablet of drug with limited permeability using novel surfactant binder and microencapsulated polysorbate: In vitro/in vivo evaluation*. PubMed. Retrieved June 5, 2025, from <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/26086847/>
- Fantini, A., Giulio, L., Delledonne, A., Pescina, S., Sissa, C., Nicoli, S., Santi, P., & Padula, C. (2022, December 30). *Buccal Permeation of Polysaccharide High Molecular Weight Compounds: Effect of Chemical Permeation Enhancers*. PubMed Central. Retrieved June 4, 2025, from <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC9864332/>
- Fortuna, A., Sonvico, F., & Schindowski, K. (2022, March 1). *Editorial: Intranasal Drug Delivery: Challenges and Opportunities*. Frontiers. Retrieved June 4, 2025, from <https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/pharmacology/articles/10.3389/fphar.2022.868986/full>
- Fouad, S. A., Shamma, R. N., Basalious, E. B., El-Nabarawi, M. A., & Tayel, S. A. (2016, April 5). *Novel instantly-soluble transmucosal matrix (ISTM) using dual mechanism solubilizer for sublingual and nasal delivery of dapoxetine hydrochloride: In-vitro/in-vivo evaluation*. PubMed. Retrieved June 4, 2025, from <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/27063851/>
- Frothingham, S. (2018, September 27). *pH of Saliva*. Healthline. Retrieved June 4, 2025, from <https://www.healthline.com/health/ph-of-saliva>
- Genentech USA, Inc. (2024). *Dosing & Administration Guidelines for Activase® (alteplase)*. activase. Retrieved June 3, 2025, from <https://www.activase.com/ais/dosing-and-administration/dosing.html>

- Greineder, C. F., Howard, M. D., Carnemolla, R., Cines, D. B., & Muzykantov, V. R. (2013, August 29). *Advanced drug delivery systems for antithrombotic agents*. Ash Publications. Retrieved June 5, 2025, from <https://ashpublications.org/blood/article/122/9/1565/32190/Advanced-drug-delivery-systems-for-antithrombotic>
- Harmon, F., Masson-Lunven, C., Boutière, B., Boyer-Neumann, C., Larrieu, M. J., & Anglés-Cano, E. (1990, October 1). *Factors affecting the stability of tPA and PAI-1 during storage and handling of human plasma for in vitro studies: implications in the determination of tPA and PAI-1 activities*. PubMed. Retrieved June 4, 2025, from <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/2133216/>
- Huang, Y., Yu, L., Ren, J., Gu, B., Longstaff, C., Hughes, A. D., Thom, S. A., Xu, X. Y., & Chen, R. (2019, April 28). *An activated-platelet-sensitive nanocarrier enables targeted delivery of tissue plasminogen activator for effective thrombolytic therapy*. ScienceDirect. Retrieved June 5, 2025, from <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0168365919301166>
- Jilani, T. N., & Siddiqui, A. H. (2023, February 20). *Tissue Plasminogen Activator - StatPearls*. NCBI. Retrieved June 3, 2025, from <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK507917/>
- Jonaitis, L., Marković, S., Farkas, K., Gheorghe, L., Krznarić, Ž., Salupere, R., Mokricka, V., Spassova, Z., Gatev, D., Grosu, I., Lijović, A., Mitrović, O., Saje, M., Schafer, E., Uršič, V., Roblek, T., & Drobne, D. (2021, December 9). *Intravenous versus subcutaneous delivery of biotherapeutics in IBD: an expert's and patient's perspective*. PubMed Central. Retrieved June 6, 2025, from <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC8654488/>

- Kang, Z.-L., Kong, L.-H., Hu, Z., Li, Y.-P., & Ma, H.-J. (2023, January 9). *Effect of sodium bicarbonate and sodium chloride on protein conformation and gel properties of pork myofibrillar protein*. *Arabian Journal of Chemistry*. Retrieved June 5, 2025, from <https://arabjchem.org/effect-of-sodium-bicarbonate-and-sodium-chloride-on-protein-conformation-and-gel-properties-of-pork-myofibrillar-protein/>
- Kim, G. C., Cheon, D. H., & Lee, Y. (2021, April 4). *Challenge to overcome current limitations of cell-penetrating peptides*. *ScienceDirect*. Retrieved June 4, 2025, from <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S1570963921000108>
- Kim, H., Kim, J.-T., Lee, J. S., Kim, B. J., Park, J.-M., Kang, K., Lee, S. J., Kim, J. G., Cha, J.-K., Kim, D.-H., Park, T. H., Park, S.-S., Lee, K. B., Lee, J., Hong, K.-S., Cho, Y.-J., Park, H.-K., Lee, B.-C., Yu, K.-H., ... Bae, H.-J. (2021, January 31). *Golden Hour Thrombolysis in Acute Ischemic Stroke: The Changing Pattern in South Korea*. *Journal of Stroke*. Retrieved June 3, 2025, from <https://www.j-stroke.org/m/journal/view.php?number=366>
- Kurth, T., Glynn, R. J., Walker, A. M., Chan, K. A., Buring, J. E., Hennekens, C. H., & Gaziano, J. M. (2003, August 25). *Inhibition of Clinical Benefits of Aspirin on First Myocardial Infarction by Nonsteroidal Antiinflammatory Drugs*. *AHA Journals*. Retrieved June 3, 2025, from <https://www.ahajournals.org/doi/10.1161/01.cir.0000087593.07533.9b>
- Long, X., Gou, Y., Luo, M., Zhang, S., Zhang, H., Bai, L., Wu, S., He, Q., Chen, K., Huang, A., Zhou, J., & Wang, D. (2015, March 1). *Soluble expression, purification, and characterization of active recombinant human tissue plasminogen activator by auto-induction in E. coli*. *PubMed Central*. Retrieved June 4, 2025, from <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC4379951/>

- Longstaff, C., Thelwell, C., Williams, S. C., Silva, M. M. C. G., Kolev, K., & Szabó, L. (2011, January 13). *The interplay between tissue plasminogen activator domains and fibrin structures in the regulation of fibrinolysis: kinetic and microscopic studies*. Ash Publications. Retrieved June 3, 2025, from <https://ashpublications.org/blood/article/117/2/661/28163/The-interplay-between-tissue-plasminogen-activator>
- Lou, J., Duan, H., Qin, Q., Teng, Z., Gan, F., Zhou, X., & Zhou, X. (2023, February 1). *Advances in Oral Drug Delivery Systems: Challenges and Opportunities*. PubMed Central. Retrieved June 4, 2025, from <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC9960885/>
- Lu, Q., Shi, K., Wang, Y., & Shi, F.-D. (2023, September 7). *Neurovascular Inflammation and Complications of Thrombolysis Therapy in Stroke*. AHA Journals. Retrieved June 5, 2025, from <https://www.ahajournals.org/doi/10.1161/STROKEAHA.123.044123>
- Moroz, E., Matorri, S., & Leroux, J.-C. (2016, January 27). *Oral delivery of macromolecular drugs: Where we are after almost 100 years of attempts*. ScienceDirect. Retrieved June 6, 2025, from <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0169409X16300278>
- Pannell, R., Li, S., & Gurewich, V. (2015, March 26). *Highly Effective Fibrinolysis by a Sequential Synergistic Combination of Mini-Dose tPA plus Low-Dose Mutant proUK*. PubMed Central. Retrieved June 6, 2025, from <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC4374801/>

- Saver, J. L., Gornbein, J., Grotta, J., Liebeskind, D., Lutsep, H., Schwamm, L., Scott, P., & Starkman, S. (2009, June 4). *Number Needed to Treat to Benefit and to Harm for Intravenous Tissue Plasminogen Activator Therapy in the 3- to 4.5-Hour Window: Joint Outcome Table Analysis of the ECASS 3 Trial*. AHA Journals. Retrieved June 6, 2025, from <https://www.ahajournals.org/doi/full/10.1161/STROKEAHA.108.543561>
- Sebaaly, C., Trifan, A., Sieniawska, E., & Greige-Gerges, H. (2021, March 1). *Chitosan-Coating Effect on the Characteristics of Liposomes: A Focus on Bioactive Compounds and Essential Oils: A Review*. MDPI. Retrieved June 5, 2025, from <https://www.mdpi.com/2227-9717/9/3/445>
- Shen, M., Wang, Y., Hu, F., Lv, L., Chen, K., & Xing, G. (2021, November 10). *Thrombolytic Agents: Nanocarriers in Targeted Release*. PubMed Central. Retrieved June 5, 2025, from <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC8619279/>
- UTMB Health. (n.d.). *Neurosciences - Stroke Facts*. UTMB Health. Retrieved June 3, 2025, from <https://www.utmbhealth.com/services/neurology/procedures-conditions/stroke/stroke-facts>
- Williams, D. O. (2004, April 20). *Treatment Delayed Is Treatment Denied*. AHA Journals. Retrieved June 3, 2025, from <https://www.ahajournals.org/doi/full/10.1161/01.CIR.0000126892.17646.83>
- World Health Organization. (2021). *Cardiovascular diseases*. World Health Organization (WHO). Retrieved June 2, 2025, from <https://www.who.int/health-topics/cardiovascular-diseases>

Wu, J., Jones, N., Hohenwarter, L., Zhao, F., Chan, V., Tan, Z., Morin, T., Li, J., Kaur, T.,

Andrew, L. J., Ross, C. J.D., Hedtrich, S., & Li, S.-D. (2024, March 4). *Systemic delivery of proteins using novel peptides via the sublingual route*. Pharma Excipients.

Retrieved June 5, 2025, from

<https://www.pharmaexcipients.com/news/systemic-delivery-proteins/>

Yang, D., Sun, Y.-Y., Lin, X., Baumann, J. M., Dunn, R. S., Lindquist, D. M., & Kuan, C.-Y.

(2013, January 23). *Intranasal Delivery of Cell-Penetrating anti-NF- κ B Peptides (Tat-NBD) Alleviates Infection-Sensitized Hypoxic-Ischemic Brain Injury*. PubMed

Central. Retrieved June 4, 2025, from

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC4064308/>

Yartsev, A. (2021, August 16). *Fibrinolytic and antifibrinolytic agents*. Deranged Physiology.

Retrieved June 6, 2025, from

<https://derangedphysiology.com/main/cicm-primary-exam/haematological-system/Chapter-225/fibrinolytic-and-antifibrinolytic-agents>